

Mining Educational Data to Support Students' Major Selection

Authors : Kunyanuth Kularbphettong, Cholticha Tongsi

Abstract : This paper aims to create the model for student in choosing an emphasized track of student majoring in computer science at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The objective of this research is to develop the suggested system using data mining technique to analyze knowledge and conduct decision rules. Such relationships can be used to demonstrate the reasonableness of student choosing a track as well as to support his/her decision and the system is verified by experts in the field. The sampling is from student of computer science based on the system and the questionnaire to see the satisfaction. The system result is found to be satisfactory by both experts and student as well.

Keywords : data mining technique, the decision support system, knowledge and decision rules, education

Conference Title : ICEIT 2014 : International Conference on Educational and Instructional Technology

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : January 20-21, 2014